

Multiword Expressions in Syntactic and Semantic Parsing Environments (MWE-SemPrE)

Final report

1 General information

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2 Summary

2.1 German summary

Mehrwortausdrücke (MWEs) sind Kombinationen aus mehreren Lexemen, deren Gesamteigenschaften sich nicht ohne Weiteres aus denen ihrer Bestandteile ableiten lassen. Ein bekanntes Beispiel ist der englische Ausdruck *kick the bucket*, dessen Gesamtbedeutung („sterben“) sich nicht aus der Kombination der Bedeutungen seiner Bestandteile erschließen lässt. Diese Eigenart, die im MWE-Kontext üblicherweise als Idiomaticität bezeichnet wird, macht MWEs zu einer Herausforderung für die automatische Sprachverarbeitung (NLP), und die hohe Verbreitung dieses Phänomens zwingt uns dazu, Wege zu finden, mit diesem Phänomen umzugehen. Verbale MWEs (VMWEs) sind aufgrund von Eigenschaften wie Diskontinuität, Überlappung, variierender Wortstellung und syntaktischer oder semantischer Mehrdeutigkeit besonders schwierig hinsichtlich ihrer Verarbeitung. In letzter Zeit wurde im Bereich der NLP-Forschung viel Arbeit in die Identifizierung von MWEs und die Kombination der MWE-Identifizierung mit syntaktischer Analyse investiert (siehe beispielsweise das europäische PARSEME-Projekt). Die Identifizierung ist zusammen mit einer Darstellung ihrer idiomatischen Bedeutungen eine Voraussetzung für die erfolgreiche semantische Analyse von MWEs. Die meisten aktuellen semantischen Parser decken jedoch entweder nicht-wörtliche Lesarten von MWEs überhaupt nicht oder nur in sehr begrenztem Umfang ab. MWE-SemPrE befasst sich mit diesem Problem und zielt darauf ab, die MWE-Identifizierung mit der syntaktischen Analyse zu integrieren und den Ansatz auf einen MWE-fähigen semantischen Parser auszuweiten. Der Schwerpunkt liegt dabei auf VMWEs und Architekturen auf der Grundlage von syntaktischen Dependenzbäumen und semantischen Repräsentationen der Diskursrepräsentationstheorie (DRT), in Kombination mit einer MWE-spezifischen Erweiterung der Parallel Meaning Bank (PMB, Abzianidze et al., 2017, 2020). Ursprünglich war im Projekt geplant, eine (syntaktische und semantische) Parsingarchitektur basierend auf Gram-

matikformalismen mit erweiterter Lokalitätsdomäne und auf Supertagging zu entwickeln. Im Laufe der Projektarbeit stellte sich jedoch ein Ansatz mit einer Seq-to-Seq Transformerarchitektur, die die Eingabe direkt in eine sequentielle Repräsentation von Diskursrepräsentationsstrukturen (DRS) übersetzt, als erfolgreicher heraus.

2.2 English summary

Multiword expressions (MWEs) are combinations of multiple lexemes whose overall properties are not readily predictable by those of their components. A well-known example is the expression *kick the bucket*, whose overall meaning ('die') cannot be derived by combining the meanings of its constituents. This idiosyncrasy, which is usually termed idiomaticity in the MWE context, makes MWEs a challenge for natural language processing (NLP), and their ubiquity forces us to find ways to account for them. Verbal MWEs (VMWEs) are particularly challenging because of properties like discontinuity, overlap, varying word order, and syntactic or semantic ambiguity. Recently, a considerable amount of NLP research has been done on identifying MWEs and on combining MWE identification with syntactic parsing (see, for example, the European PARSEME project). This, together with a representation of their idiomatic meanings, is a prerequisite for successful semantic parsing of MWEs. Most current semantic parsers, however, either do not cover non-literal readings of MWEs at all or only in a very limited way. MWE-SemPrE addresses this problem and aimed at integrating MWE identification with syntactic parsing, and extending the approach to an MWE-aware semantic parser. The focus was mainly on VMWEs and architectures based on dependency trees and Discourse Representation Theory (DRT), in combination with an MWE-specific extension of the Parallel Meaning Bank (PMB, Abzianidze et al., 2017, 2020). We originally planned (syntactic and semantic) parsing architectures based on some notion of extended domain of locality and supertagging. The project deviated from this, adopting rather seq-to-seq transformer architectures for parsing that translate the input into sequence representations of DRSs.

3 Progress report

Over the project duration, MWE-SemPrE has contributed to the following research aims:

1. (WP1) Annotating resources for semantic representations of verbal MWEs, more specifically of verbal idioms.
2. (WP2) Understanding the relation between MWE identification and syntactic parsing.
3. (WP3) Developing VID-sensitive models of semantic parsing.

3.1 VMWE annotations

This part of the project concerns WP1: *Correcting VMWE annotations in the PMB*. The objective is to create a dataset that includes full semantic representations of sentences containing verbal multiword expressions (VMWEs) in order to train and evaluate semantic parsers wrt. such expressions. To this end, we planned to extend part of the Parallel Meaning Bank (PMB) for English and German in an annotation effort focused on potential VMWEs. VMWEs are one area where the annotation guidelines of the PMB are not yet fully worked out and as a consequence, annotation is incomplete, so this effort will not only benefit our project but also the PMB.

For this part of the project we closely collaborated with the PMB group in Groningen, in particular with Johan Bos. It consisted of the following two steps:

1. Extracting German PIEs (possibly idiomatic expressions) from the PMB and annotating them: We first selected candidate idiomatic expressions, then determined their idiomaticity status and whether they are decomposable or not, and then we annotated their semantics using WordNet (Fellbaum, 1998) senses and VerbNet (Kipper Schuler, 2005) semantic roles. Overall, inter-annotator agreement was satisfying. A challenge, however, was to choose the correct word sense. This is not surprising, given that the task was to map German idioms onto English synsets.
2. Integrating the resulting annotations into the DRS representations in the PMB.

The two steps and the resulting resource is described in Ehren et al. (2024), and the annotated data are published in Ehren et al. (2025), including annotation guidelines.

3.2 Syntactic parsing and MWE identification

The starting point for this part of the project was WP2: *MWE-aware syntactic parsing*. The original goal of WP 2 was to propose a parsing architecture which will allow to handle MWE identification jointly with syntactic parsing. We slightly modified this by addressing the question whether syntactic parsing (or, alternatively, available syntactic information) improves the quality of MWE identification.

In order to answer this, the following experiments were conducted:

1. Multi-task learning: We trained a Transformer-based model to jointly identify syntactic dependencies and MWEs. In order to find an appropriate weighting for the losses of the two tasks, we used dynamic weighting based on homoscedastic uncertainty. Although dynamic weighting improved results compared to no weighting, MWE identification as a single-task was not outperformed by the joint approach.¹
2. Contrastive learning: Instead of using dependency parsing as an auxiliary task, we now experimented with different types of enhanced word representations, optimized either for a semantic similarity or a syntactic similarity objective. We again obtained a negative result; none of the optimized embeddings was able to outperform the BERT baseline on MWE identification.²

This work is described in Ehren et al. (2026).

3.3 MWEs in semantic parsing

The following results were obtained in WP 3: *MWE-aware semantic parsing*. WP 3 is concerned with the development of semantic parsers that are capable of correctly interpreting MWEs and distinguishing between idiomatic MWEs and literal uses. The focus is on verbal MWEs but other classes might be included as well. We mainly focussed on parsing to DRSs. In the early stages of this WP (while waiting for the PMB data to be ready), we also tried other architectures. This WP yielded the following results:

1. Semantic parsing with an architecture that combines TAG and frames (Bladier et al., 2023)³. This approach performs parsing towards semantic frames on the PMB data (though, at the time, without the additional VMWE annotations). It was one of the architectures we planned to extend to VID-sensitive semantic parsing.

¹The code is available here: https://github.com/rafehr/mwe_tagger

²The code is available here: <https://gitlab.com/mwesempre/mtlb-depmwe-full>

³The code is available here: <https://github.com/TaniaBladier/Frame-Semantic-Parser-with-Lexicalized-Grammars>.

2. DRS parsing as sequence labeling (Shen & Evang, 2022)⁴. Another approach that we tried out early on the PMB data was to frame semantic parsing as sequence labeling, inspired by similar approaches for syntactic parsing such as Gómez-Rodríguez & Vilares (2018).
3. VID-sensitive semantic parsing towards DRSs as a seq-to-seq task (Evang et al., 2025b)⁵. Our final choice for VID-sensitive DRS parsing, inspired by Wang et al. (2023), was to frame the task as a seq-to-seq translation from the input sentence to a sequence representation of the DRS (Bos, 2023).

The experiments in this paper show that given appropriate training data (i.e., with VID annotations), the model can learn to predict the idiomatic meanings and improve performance also for literal readings, even though predicting the correct concepts in context remains challenging.

3.4 Further results on processing and annotation of VMWEs

Besides results connected to a specific WP, we also worked on related project topics that were not restricted to a single WP:

1. In preparation of WP 2, and in order to achieve a better understanding of VMWEs, we conducted an analysis of a MWE identification model tracing its attention patterns (Ehren et al., 2022).
2. Besides the enrichment of the PMB with VID annotation, we also contributed to other efforts to construct MWE-aware lexicon and corpus resources (Barbu Mititelu et al., 2024), collaborating with the MWE research community and the UniDive COST Action⁶.

3.5 Dissemination activities

Events for dissemination and exchange within the research community. Besides presenting our results at conferences and research seminars, the project also contributed to organizing international events that foster the exchange of results and ideas in the areas of MWEs and of computational semantics. Concretely, the project was involved in the following conference/workshop organizations:

1. As an important contribution to the research community around the topic of MWE processing in NLP, we were involved in the organization of the two MWE workshops in 2023 and 2024 (Bhatia et al., 2023, 2024).
2. Furthermore, as a more general outreach to the research community, we organized the *16th International Conference on Computational Semantics* in Düsseldorf in September 2025⁷. As part of this, we also edited the proceedings published in the ACL anthology (Evang et al., 2025c).

3.6 Research data

The project produced two types of research data (beyond the published articles), namely annotations and code. All data was made publicly available, i.e., open access/open source.

⁴The code is available here: <https://github.com/ShenMinX/DRS-parser>

⁵The code is available at <https://gitlab.com/mwesempre/idiompb> and also published as part of Evang et al. (2025a).

⁶<https://www.cost.eu/actions/CA21167/>

⁷<https://iwcs2025.github.io/>

1. Ehren et al. (2025): Dataset of the annotated VMWEs from the PMB comprising the annotation guidelines and the annotated data itself. The dataset is described in Ehren et al. (2024). Its integration into the PMB is ongoing.
2. Evang et al. (2025a): Code and data of the experiments reported in Evang et al. (2025b).
3. The source code for the other project results has been published on GitHub or GitLab, see the corresponding footnotes above.

3.7 Summary: Main contributions

The research conducted in this project has considerably improved our understanding of the way verbal MWEs interact with their environment and how they are linked to syntactic features (Ehren et al., 2022, 2026). An important project contribution is the annotation of verbal idioms in the PMB with appropriate semantic representations, including not only decisions about idiomaticity versus literal readings but also decisions about how to choose appropriate senses (Ehren et al., 2024, 2025). Given the ongoing integration into the PMB, which is a widely used standard resource for semantic parsing, we expect this work to have a lasting impact. Finally, the project has successfully implemented a range of different novel architectures for semantic parsing, including a VID-sensitive model (Bladier et al., 2023; Shen & Evang, 2022; Evang et al., 2025b,a). In particular the latter is to our knowledge the first semantic parsing model that is optimized and explicitly evaluated for appropriately dealing with VMWEs. As such, it sets a new state-of-the-art for semantic VID parsing.

Bibliography

- Abzianidze, L., J. Bjerva, K. Evang, H. Haagsma, R. van Noord, P. Ludmann, D.-D. Nguyen & J. Bos. 2017. The Parallel Meaning Bank: Towards a Multilingual Corpus of Translations Annotated with Compositional Meaning Representations. In M. Lapata, P. Blunsom & A. Koller (eds.), *Proceedings of the 15th Conference of the European Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Volume 2, Short Papers*, 242–247. Valencia, Spain: Association for Computational Linguistics. URL <https://aclanthology.org/E17-2039/>.
- Abzianidze, L., R. van Noord, C. Wang & J. Bos. 2020. The Parallel Meaning Bank: A Framework for Semantically Annotating Multiple Languages. *Applied mathematics and informatics* 25(2). 45–60.
- Barbu Mititelu, V., V. Giouli, K. Evang, D. Zeman, P. Osenova, C. Tiberius, S. Krek, S. Markantonatou, I. Stoyanova, R. Stanković & C. Chiarcos. 2024. Multiword Expressions between the Corpus and the Lexicon: Universality, Idiosyncrasy, and the Lexicon-Corpus Interface. In A. Bhatia, G. Bouma, A. S. Doğruöz, K. Evang, M. Garcia, V. Giouli, L. Han, J. Nivre & A. Rademaker (eds.), *Proceedings of the Joint Workshop on Multiword Expressions and Universal Dependencies (MWE-UD) @ LREC-COLING 2024*, 147–153. Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2024.mwe-1.19/>.
- Bhatia, A., G. Bouma, A. S. Doğruöz, K. Evang, M. Garcia, V. Giouli, L. Han, J. Nivre & A. Rademaker (eds.). 2024. *Proceedings of the Joint Workshop on Multiword Expressions and Universal Dependencies (MWE-UD) @ LREC-COLING 2024*. Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2024.mwe-1.0/>.
- Bhatia, A., K. Evang, M. Garcia, V. Giouli, L. Han & S. Taslimipoor (eds.). 2023. *Proceedings of the 19th Workshop on Multiword Expressions (MWE 2023)*. Dubrovnik, Croatia: Association for Computational Linguistics. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2023.mwe-1.0/>.
- Bladier, T., L. Kallmeyer & K. Evang. 2023. Data-Driven Frame-Semantic Parsing with Tree Wrapping Grammar. In M. Amblard & E. Breitholtz (eds.), *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Computational Semantics*, 223–232. Nancy, France: Association for Computational Linguistics. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2023.iwcs-1.22/>.

- Bos, J. 2023. The Sequence Notation: Catching Complex Meanings in Simple Graphs. In M. Amblard & E. Breitholtz (eds.), *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Computational Semantics*, 195–208. Nancy, France: Association for Computational Linguistics. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2023.iwcs-1.20/>.
- Ehren, R., K. Evang & L. Kallmeyer. 2024. To Leave No Stone Unturned: Annotating Verbal Idioms in the Parallel Meaning Bank. In A. Bhatia, G. Bouma, A. S. Doğruöz, K. Evang, M. Garcia, V. Giouli, L. Han, J. Nivre & A. Rademaker (eds.), *Proceedings of the Joint Workshop on Multiword Expressions and Universal Dependencies (MWE-UD) @ LREC-COLING 2024*, 115–124. Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2024.mwe-1.16/>.
- Ehren, R., K. Evang & L. Kallmeyer. 2025. PMB-VID, Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15525158. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525158>.
- Ehren, R., L. Kallmeyer & T. Lichte. 2022. An Analysis of Attention in German Verbal Idiom Disambiguation. In A. Bhatia, P. Cook, S. Taslimipoor, M. Garcia & C. Ramisch (eds.), *Proceedings of the 18th Workshop on Multiword Expressions @LREC2022*, 16–25. Marseille, France: European Language Resources Association. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2022.mwe-1.5/>.
- Ehren, R., D. E. Yavaş, K. Evang & L. Kallmeyer. 2026. The Relationship between Parsing and Verbal MWE Identification: It's Complicated. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18954698. Technical report. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18954698>.
- Evang, K., R. Ehren & L. Kallmeyer. 2025a. PMB-VID-parsing. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17226015. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17226015>.
- Evang, K., R. Ehren & L. Kallmeyer. 2025b. The Proper Treatment of Verbal Idioms in German Discourse Representation Structure Parsing. In K. Evang, L. Kallmeyer & S. Pogodalla (eds.), *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Computational Semantics*, 156–165. Düsseldorf, Germany: Association for Computational Linguistics. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2025.iwcs-main.15/>.
- Evang, K., L. Kallmeyer & S. Pogodalla (eds.). 2025c. *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Computational Semantics*. Düsseldorf, Germany: Association for Computational Linguistics. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2025.iwcs-main.0/>.
- Fellbaum, C. 1998. *WordNet: An electronic lexical database*. MIT Press.
- Gómez-Rodríguez, C. & D. Vilares. 2018. Constituent Parsing as Sequence Labeling. In E. Riloff, D. Chiang, J. Hockenmaier & J. Tsujii (eds.), *Proceedings of the 2018 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, 1314–1324. Brussels, Belgium: Association for Computational Linguistics. doi: 10.18653/v1/D18-1162. URL <https://aclanthology.org/D18-1162/>.
- Kipper Schuler, K. 2005. *VerbNet: A Broad-Coverage, Comprehensive Verb Lexicon*: University of Pennsylvania dissertation.
- Shen, M. & K. Evang. 2022. DRS Parsing as Sequence Labeling. In V. Nastase, E. Pavlick, M. T. Pilehvar, J. Camacho-Collados & A. Raganato (eds.), *Proceedings of the 11th Joint Conference on Lexical and Computational Semantics*, 213–225. Seattle, Washington: Association for Computational Linguistics. doi: 10.18653/v1/2022.starsem-1.19. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2022.starsem-1.19/>.
- Wang, C., H. Lai, M. Nissim & J. Bos. 2023. Pre-Trained Language-Meaning Models for Multilingual Parsing and Generation. In A. Rogers, J. Boyd-Graber & N. Okazaki (eds.), *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: ACL 2023*, 5586–5600. Toronto, Canada: Association for Computational Linguistics. doi: 10.18653/v1/2023.findings-acl.345. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2023.findings-acl.345/>.

4 Published Project Results

4.1 Category A – Articles in peer-reviewed journals, contributions to peer-reviewed conferences or to anthology volumes, and book publications

All the publications listed in the following are open access.

- Barbu Mititelu, V., V. Giouli, K. Evang, D. Zeman, P. Osenova, C. Tiberius, S. Krek, S. Markantonatou, I. Stoyanova, R. Stanković & C. Chiarcos. 2024. Multiword Expressions between the Corpus and the Lexicon: Universality, Idiosyncrasy, and the Lexicon-Corpus Interface. In A. Bhatia, G. Bouma, A. S. Doğruöz, K. Evang, M. Garcia, V. Giouli, L. Han, J. Nivre & A. Rademaker (eds.), *Proceedings of the Joint Workshop on Multiword Expressions and Universal Dependencies (MWE-UD) @ LREC-COLING 2024*, 147–153. Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2024.mwe-1.19/>
- Bhatia, A., K. Evang, M. Garcia, V. Giouli, L. Han & S. Taslimipoor (eds.). 2023. *Proceedings of the 19th Workshop on Multiword Expressions (MWE 2023)*. Dubrovnik, Croatia: Association for Computational Linguistics. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2023.mwe-1.0/>
- Bhatia, A., G. Bouma, A. S. Doğruöz, K. Evang, M. Garcia, V. Giouli, L. Han, J. Nivre & A. Rademaker (eds.). 2024. *Proceedings of the Joint Workshop on Multiword Expressions and Universal Dependencies (MWE-UD) @ LREC-COLING 2024*. Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2024.mwe-1.0/>
- Bladier, T., L. Kallmeyer & K. Evang. 2023. Data-Driven Frame-Semantic Parsing with Tree Wrapping Grammar. In M. Amblard & E. Breitholtz (eds.), *Proceedings of the 15th International Conference on Computational Semantics*, 223–232. Nancy, France: Association for Computational Linguistics. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2023.iwcs-1.22/>
- Ehren, R., K. Evang & L. Kallmeyer. 2024. To Leave No Stone Unturned: Annotating Verbal Idioms in the Parallel Meaning Bank. In A. Bhatia, G. Bouma, A. S. Doğruöz, K. Evang, M. Garcia, V. Giouli, L. Han, J. Nivre & A. Rademaker (eds.), *Proceedings of the Joint Workshop on Multiword Expressions and Universal Dependencies (MWE-UD) @ LREC-COLING 2024*, 115–124. Torino, Italia: ELRA and ICCL. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2024.mwe-1.16/>
- Ehren, R., L. Kallmeyer & T. Lichte. 2022. An Analysis of Attention in German Verbal Idiom Disambiguation. In A. Bhatia, P. Cook, S. Taslimipoor, M. Garcia & C. Ramisch (eds.), *Proceedings of the 18th Workshop on Multiword Expressions @LREC2022*, 16–25. Marseille, France: European Language Resources Association. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2022.mwe-1.5/>
- Evang, K., R. Ehren & L. Kallmeyer. 2025b. The Proper Treatment of Verbal Idioms in German Discourse Representation Structure Parsing. In K. Evang, L. Kallmeyer & S. Pogodalla (eds.), *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Computational Semantics*, 156–165. Düsseldorf, Germany: Association for Computational Linguistics. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2025.iwcs-main.15/>
- Shen, M. & K. Evang. 2022. DRS Parsing as Sequence Labeling. In V. Nastase, E. Pavlick, M. T. Pilehvar, J. Camacho-Collados & A. Raganato (eds.), *Proceedings of the 11th Joint Conference on Lexical and Computational Semantics*, 213–225. Seattle, Washington: Association for Computational Linguistics. doi: 10.18653/v1/2022.starsem-1.19. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2022.starsem-1.19/>

4.2 Category B – Any other form of published results

- Ehren, R., K. Evang & L. Kallmeyer. 2025. PMB-VID, Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15525158. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525158>
- Evang, K., R. Ehren & L. Kallmeyer. 2025a. PMB-VID-parsing. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17226015. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17226015>
- Ehren, R., D. E. Yavaş, K. Evang & L. Kallmeyer. 2026. The Relationship between Parsing and Verbal MWE Identification: It’s Complicated. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18954698. Technical report. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18954698>

4.3 Patents (applied for and granted)

None.